

Structural, morphological and optical characterisation of electrodeposited ZnSe thin films

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Abstract : The basic aim of this study is to present the room temperature synthesis of ZnSe thin film by varying doping concentration of selenium oxide on ITO plate using a relatively simple and low cost traditional electrodeposition technique. X-Ray diffraction confirms the formation of single cubic ZnSe phase with a preferred orientation along (111) direction with an average value of the crystallite size around 37 nm. Optical studies reveal a transmittance above 80% for lower SeO₂ concentration (< 3%) then drop up to 60% for higher concentration (> 5%) with an energy bandgap around 2.75 eV. Photoluminescence analysis shows the presence of mainly 2 bands, narrow PL band centered at 487 nm and broad photoemission band centered at 531 nm. Scanning electron microscopy observations reveal the formation of dense nanostructured films.

Keywords : ITO plate, ZnSe, electrodeposition, photoluminescence, energy bandgap.

Introduction

World's energy demands are met from a variety of energy sources, both conventional and non-commercial. In spite of substantial increase during the last many decades in the supply of commercial sources of energy such as coal, oil and electricity, non-commercial sources dominated by fuel wood still meet around half of our energy needs, particularly in the rural areas. Besides, being inefficient in terms of end use, loss of green wood for fuel also results in adverse impact on the environment and pollution control. There exists a substantial potential in non-conventional sources such as solar, wind and tidal energy etc. Considering the factors of continued consump-

tion for long run, it is possible to have sustainable energy by tapping renewable energy sources particularly solar energy which is available in plenty. Solar energy conversion is mainly classified as solar thermal energy and solar photovoltaics electricity.

The direct conversion of solar energy in to electricity by photovoltaic (PV) solar cells was studied for the past 30 years^{1,2}. We are still far from making these sources cost effective. Photovoltaic solar energy conversion offers one of the few ways of producing electricity in urban areas which is free of various emissions and noise. Functional considerations, and in particular efficiency, dominated research and development, when terrestrial PV

applications were developed, the same considerations of functionality and efficiency continued to be given priority among them ZnSe, CdSe and doped-CdSe thin films are in queues³. The present thesis gives a brief account of thin film solar cells.

Thin films of group II-VI semiconductor compounds have attracted considerable attention due to their novel physical properties^{4,5}. As a wide bandgap material, ZnSe is a talented candidate showing compatibility for optoelectronic devices based on the thinfilm technology^{5,6}. The substantial interest over the years owing to their wide range of applications in various optoelectronic applications and current developments go hand-in-hand with the explosion of scientific and technological breakthroughs in microelectronics, optics and nanotechnology⁷⁻⁹.

The major technical importance of semiconductor ZnSe thin films is exhibiting simultaneously high electrical conductivity and optical transparency. For example in solar cells flat panel displays and electronic devices. The nanocrystalline II-VI films are prospective for development of resistive sensors, operating at room temperature. There also exists interest in inclusion of ternary alloys of II-VI semiconductors in low-dimensional structures¹⁰⁻¹³. Since they offer possibilities to change their lattice constant and optical properties by changing the composition and this gives them some advantages over binary compounds. For the preparation of ternary ZnSe layers epitaxial techniques^{14,15} and electro deposition are most frequently used and even the epitaxial growth methods produce compositionally disordered films.

ZnSe is the most popular material for infrared applications because of its high refractive index (2.417–2.385 at 8–13 nm), low dispersion rate at infrared (IR) wavelengths, and towering transmission band from 0.60 nm to 20 nm. ZnSe is a competitive material compared to the other thin film materials owing its compatibility¹⁶. Thin films of this material can be deposited by using a variety of methods, including pulsed laser ablation, electron beam deposition, magnetron sputtering, and atomic layer deposition¹⁷⁻¹⁹. While the we used electro deposition method which offers many advantages compared to the other sophisticated techniques, like reproducibility, simple mecha-

nism, high deposition rate, and economically viability, is one of the fast synthesis methods to produce high quality thin films of large scale.

Moreover, the easy substrate loading, and high deposition rate are its additional advantages. Nevertheless, thin films synthesized at higher temperature have been studied and investigated over the years including ZnSe; however, achieving high quality thin films at room temperature is rather challenging.

Over the last few years, the family of wide bandgap II-VI semiconductors have been widely studied due to their fundamental electronic and optical properties. Among them, ZnSe, with a direct bandgap of 2.67 eV at 300 K, is very attractive materials for various optoelectronic devices, such as blue-light emitting diodes and lasers; as a window material in heterojunction solar cells, in the place of CdS. As reviewed elsewhere, electrodeposition is a simple and versatile method for preparing thin films of these materials. In this work results on the preparation and characterization of ZnSe thin films obtained by electrodeposition method.

Venkatachalam *et al.*²⁰ have reported the influence of substrate temperature on the structural, optical and electrical properties of zinc selenide (ZnSe) thin films. Zinc selenide (ZnSe) thin films were deposited onto well cleaned silicon (100) and glass substrates at different substrate temperature (483–589 K) using vacuum evaporation method under a vacuum of 4×10^{-3} Pa. The compositions of the deposited films were determined by Rutherford backscattering spectrometry and the percentage of iodine concentration is calculated as (ZnSe) I_{0.001}. The X-ray diffractograms reveal the cubic structure of the film oriented along the (111) direction. In optical studies, the transition of the deposited film is found to be a direct allowed transition. The optical energy gaps of the deposited films are found to be in the range from 2.72 to 2.60 eV. ZnSe/Silicon Schottky diodes were fabricated. From the current-voltage measurement the ideality factor was found to be in the range 2.01–3.51. From the capacitance-voltage studies, the built in potential was found to be 1.51 V. The values of effective carrier concentration (N_A) and the barrier height are calculated as 4.37×10^{11}

cm^{-3} and 1.95 eV, respectively. Kim *et al.*²¹ have reported the effect of a ZnSe buffer layer on the surface, structural, and optical properties of the ZnTe/ZnSe/GaAs heterostructures. Lattice-mismatched ZnTe epilayers on GaAs (100) substrates with and without ZnSe buffer layers were grown by using molecular beam epitaxy. AFM, XRD and TEM measurements were performed to investigate the surface and structural properties of the ZnTe thin films. Photoluminescence, Raman scattering and TEM measurements showed that the crystallinity of a ZnTe epilayer grown on a GaAs substrate was remarkably improved by using a ZnSe buffer layer. Photoreflectance measurements showed that the strain of the ZnTe layer with the ZnSe buffer layer was smaller than that without the ZnSe buffer layer. These results indicate that ZnTe epitaxial films grown on GaAs substrates with ZnSe buffer layers hold promise for potential applications in optoelectronic devices operating in the blue-green spectral region. de Moraes *et al.*²² have reported the growth and properties of electrodeposited ZnSe-Fe and ZnSe-Co granular films. The growth process as well as optical and magnetic properties of the ZnSe-Fe and ZnSe-Co granular films deposited electrochemically has been investigated. The ferromagnetic nanoscaled particles with multidomain structure are embedded in a ZnSe matrix with a polycrystalline structure exhibiting semiconductor behaviour at room temperature have been demonstrated. Dori Gal *et al.*²³ have reported the electrochemical deposition of ZnSe and (Zn, Cd) Se films from nanoaqueous solutions. The composition of the mixed selenides could be controlled by variation of the deposition current density, utilizing diffusion control of the low concentrations of $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$. The film composition was measured by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy and compared with the measured bandgap values extracted from optical transmission spectra. Photoelectrochemical photocurrent spectroscopy and contact potential difference (Kelvin Probe) measurements both showed changes in apparent conductivity type with Zn concentration in the electrolyte from “n-type” (low Zn) concentration to “p-type” (high Zn). Wang *et al.*²⁴ have reported the growth and characterization of ZnSe films prepared on ZnO/Si (111) templates. It was found that the as-deposited ZnSe films are highly oriented with zinc blende structure, and the preferred

crystal orientation is (111). The small X-ray diffraction (XRD) full-wide-half-maximum (FWHM) also suggests that the crystal quality of the deposited ZnSe films is reasonably good. From temperature dependent photoluminescence (PL) measurements, it was found that exciton binding energy, E_B , equals 25.6 meV for the as-prepared ZnSe/ZnO/Si (111) samples. Reiss *et al.*²⁵ have reported the luminescent ZnSe nanocrystals of high color purity. A new synthesis method of colloidal ZnSe nanocrystals exhibiting size-dependent optical properties is reported. The ZnSe quantum dots are prepared in a non-coordinating solvent (octadecane) via direct reaction of zinc stearate with selenium dissolved in trioctylphosphine. i.e. without the use of pyrophoric reagents. The photoluminescence of the resulting nanocrystals can be tuned in the spectral range 390–440 nm with constant emission line widths of the order of 15 nm. Biljana Pejova *et al.*²⁶ have reported the three dimensional confinement effect in semiconducting zinc selenide quantum dots deposited in thin film form. Experimentally measured bandgap shifts with respect to the bulk value for quantum dot thin films with various average nanocrystal sizes are compared with the predictions of the effective mass approximation model (i.e. Brus model) the hyperbolic band model, as well as of the Nosaka’s approach. It is found that the original Brus model fails to predict correctly the $\Delta E_g(R)$ dependence, the deviations from experimental data being largest for the smallest nano-crystals. However, using the Brus equations with a single modified parameter – the relative dielectric constant of the material, leads to an excellent agreement with the experimental observations. On the other hand, application of the hyperbolic band model leads to only a moderate improvement of the agreement with the experimental data in comparison to the Brus model. This conclusion is drawn on the basis of excellent agreement of the predicted $\Delta E_g(R)$ dependence according to Nosaka’s approach with our experimental data for chemically deposited ZnSe quantum dots in thin film form. Zinc selenide (ZnSe) II-VI compound semiconductor with cubic zinc blende structure and a direct band gap of 2.7 eV is found to be a very promising material for optoelectronics devices. It has either a sphalerite structure with lattice parameters $a = 3.820 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.626 \text{ \AA}$.

The aim of this study is to investigate the phase stability analysis, microstructure and optical properties of ZnSe thin films prepared by electrodeposition onto ITO substrate using various concentration of SeO_2 as source material for Se.

Materials and methods :

Electrodeposition technique was adopted for the preparation of zinc selenide (ZnSe) thin films. The chemicals used for the preparation were analytical reagent grade (99% purity, E. Merck). The electrochemical experiments were performed using a PAR scanning potentiostat (Model 362, EG&G) employing a three-electrode configuration, with the indium doped tin oxide coated conducting glass substrate as cathode, graphite plate as anode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. Before use, indium doped tin oxide substrates were treated for 15 min with ultrasonic waves in a bath of isopropanol and then rinsed with acetone. The saturated calomel electrode was introduced into the solution by lug gin capillary whose tip was placed as close as possible to the working electrode. All the experimental potentials are referred to this electrode.

An aqueous electrolytic bath containing 250 mM of ZnSO_4 with different concentrations of SeO_2 (1, 3 and 5% of ZnSO_4). When the ZnSO_4 concentration is kept below 200 mM there is no incorporation of Zn ions in the film. If the concentration of ZnSO_4 is increase above 250 mM there is an excess of Zn content in the films. It was observed that a very low $\text{pH} < 3.5$ value the films grow spontaneously at high current densities making the process uncontrollable. The rapid growth of films followed by its peeling out from the substrate is observed.

At $\text{pH} > 3.5$, precipitation of ZnSO_4 occurs in the deposition bath. At pH value around 2.5 ± 0.1 , there is controllable growth of films with current density around 10 mA cm^{-2} . Hence, the optimum value of pH for all depositions was fixed at 2.5 ± 0.1 . Deposition period was 30 min, as which uniform and adherent films were obtained. After 30 min there is a rapid growth of films followed by peeling out from the substrate. The potential of the electrolytic bath was increased or decreased from -750 mV to -650 mV . When the potential is increased -750 mV and decreased below -650 mV , there is a rapid

growth of the film followed by feeling out from the substrate itself. The potential was fixed at -700 mV versus SCE for all depositions. The optimum condition to synthesize ZnSe thin films are identified as : (i) electrolyte concentration : 250 mM of ZnSO_4 , 2.5 mM of SeO_2 and various concentrations of SeO_2 ; (ii) solution $\text{pH} : 3.0 \pm 0.1$; (iii) deposition potential : -700 mV versus SCE; (iv) bath temperature : $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and (v) deposition time : 30 min.

Thickness of the deposited films was estimated using 'stylus profilometer'. X-Ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded using X-ray (PANalytical X'Pert Pro) diffractometer equipped with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$). Photoluminescence (PL) spectra were recorded using Varian Cary Eclipse spectrophotometer employing 15 W Xe flash lamp. The surface morphology of the samples was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) Hitachi S-3400N. Optical transmittance spectrum was recorded using a JASCO-V-570 spectrophotometer.

Results and discussion

Structural characterisation by XRD :

Fig. 1 shows the evaluated XRD patterns of ZnSe films with various SeO_2 concentrations. It can be noticed that the appearance of a single diffraction peak indexed as the main (111) peak of the cubic ZnSe phase. This clearly indicates that during electrodeposition process,

Fig. 1. XRD structure of ZnSe thin films after annealing $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for an hour with 1, 3 and 5% of SeO_2 .

the particles (grains) grow along this direction thus it represents a strong preferred orientation. It is important to note the absence of additional peaks which can be attributed to impurities, thereby confirming the high purity of the as-deposited films.

The lattice parameter ‘*a*’ is determined for a cubic crystal system by considering the strongest peak (111) for ZnSe film and using the following expression :

$$a = \frac{\lambda \sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}}{2 \sin \theta} \quad (1)$$

where *h*, *k* and *l* are integers representing (*hkl*) indices, *a* is lattice constant, *d_{hkl}* is distance between two consecutive planes (*m* = 1) with lattice plane index (*hkl*). The calculated value of the lattice parameter *a* is 5.6627 Å, which is close to the reported data JCPDS card No. 88-2345.

The crystallite size was determined by means of the X-ray line broadening method using the Scherrer equation²⁷ :

$$D = \frac{0.94 \lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (2)$$

where λ is the wavelength of Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154056$ nm), β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of (*hkl*) peak at the diffracting angle 2θ . The calculated value of *D* using (111) peak as reported in Table 1, shows that the initial concentration of SeO₂ does not show any significant change in crystallite size, the average value is around 37 nm.

By utilizing the average grain size *D*, the dislocation density δ is calculated using the following relation²⁸ :

$$\delta = \frac{1}{D^2} \text{ lines/m}^2 \quad (3)$$

Table 1. Structural parameters of ZnSe JCPDS (88-2345)

Concentration of SeO ₂	Thickness (Å)	Crystallite size (nm)	Dislocation density $\times 10^{14}$ lines/m ²
1%	52	37.16	5.08
3%	50	37.29	4.99
5%	59	37.59	4.12

where *D* is crystallite size of ZnSe thin film (in nm). As reported in Table 1, it can be noticed that the change in calculated value of δ is not that significance with the increase of SeO₂ content, as the average value is around 5×10^{14} lines/m².

Fig. 2. Optical absorbance spectra of ZnSe thin films after annealing 300 °C for an hour with 1, 3 and 5% of SeO₂.

Optical properties by UV-Vis spectroscopy :

Both absorbance and transmittance spectra were recorded for the wavelength ranges 300–2500 nm (Figs. 3 and 4). It can be observed that the as-deposited ZnSe films are transparent within a large range of wavelength (higher than 350 nm) for lower SeO₂ concentration (<3%) but reduces drastically above 1500 nm for higher SeO₂ concentration (>5%).

Additionally, the observed interference fringes are the indication on the formation of continuous dense films with

Fig. 3. Optical transmittance spectra of ZnSe thin films after annealing 300 °C for an hour with 1, 3 and 5% of SeO₂.

Fig. 4. Bandgap values of ZnSe thin films after annealing 300 °C for an hour with 1, 3 and 5% of SeO₂.

low porosity, which will be confirmed lately by SEM analysis.

In order to calculate the optical band gap we used the Tauc relation²⁹ :

$$\alpha hv = B(hv - E_g)^n \quad (4)$$

where α is the absorption coefficient, B is a constant, hv energy of incident photons and exponent n depends on the type of the transition, n may have values 1/2, 2, 3/2 and 3 corresponding to the allowed direct, allowed indirect, forbidden direct and forbidden indirect transitions respectively³⁰. Since α and transmittance (T) are correlated as follows :

$$T = \exp(-\alpha L) \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha = -(\ln T)/L \quad (6)$$

where L is the thickness of the sample, for direct allowed transition ($n = 1/2$) we have :

$$(hv \ln T)^2 = B^2 L^2 (hv - E_g) \quad (7)$$

The exact value of the optical band gap is determined by extrapolating the straight-line portion of $(hv \ln T)^2$ vs hv graph to the hv axis (Fig. 5). The values of the optical band gap decreases slightly from 2.82, 2.78 and 2.75 eV with increasing SeO₂ concentration from 1, 3 and 5%, respectively. However, it can be noticed that the above values are slighter higher than the bulk value of 2.70 eV³¹, which can be attributed to quantum size effect, since the as-deposited films are composed of nano-grains

Fig. 5. Raman spectra of ZnSe thin films after annealing 300 °C for an hour with 1, 3 and 5% of SeO₂.

which was confirmed by XRD and SEM lately.

Photoluminescence (PL) analysis :

All measured PL spectra contains two main characteristic regions : the narrow PL band centered at 487 nm which is apparently caused by near-band-edge (NBE) radiative recombination and broad photoemission band around of 531 nm which is caused by the optical transitions involving deep levels in the band gap. In ZnSe, annealing results the enhancement of the low energy part of the composite band while the emission in the high energy side of the band is suppressed. On the contrary, the annealing of ZnSe has no significant effect on its PL spectrum shape. Since the emission enhancement by annealing (300 °C for 1 h) is so effective in the increase of deep-level-related emission efficiency. However, it is clearly observed an important enhancement of both peaks intensity with increasing SeO₂ concentration, while position and broadening remain unchanged.

Morphological observations :

Fig. 6 shows that the evolution of as-deposited films' microstructure grain morphological pictures of ZnSe films respectively. All the as-deposited films show spherical grains uniformly distributed along the entire ITO substrate. Each spherical grain is composed of very nano-crystallites. The grains size slightly increases with increasing SeO₂ concentration thus forming more dense thin films.

Fig. 6. SEM images of ZnSe thin films after annealing 300 °C for an hour with 1, 3 and 5% of SeO₂.

Conclusion

ZnSe thin films were successfully electrodeposited onto ITO substrates. The as-deposited films are well crystallized having cubic structures with strong preferred orientation along (111) direction and an average crystallite size around 37 nm. Optical study shows that the transparency over 80% for SeO₂ concentration below 3% then drops up to 60%. The calculated direct optical bandgap was found around 2.80 eV. Surface morphological observations show the formation of continuous dense films. PL analysis confirms that the ZnSe films coated onto ITO substrate with a moderate crystalline structure and free from defects.

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